

PRESS RELEASE

17 March 2026

NERO Free Cybersecurity Training for SMEs Now Available on the EU Digital Skills and Jobs Platform

EU-funded initiative NERO cybersecurity training resources aim to strengthen digital resilience and cyber awareness among European SMEs.

The NERO training curriculum was developed based on the latest cybersecurity research and industry experts' insights. It includes nine training modules that use scenario-based learning approaches, enabling learners to practice decision-making in realistic cybersecurity scenarios.

Discover four of the training modules published on the EU platform, offering structured training programmes that integrate innovative learning methodologies.

Basic Level

- **Module 9: KIOKU: Gamified Scenario-based Cybersecurity Training** – Scenario-based training that allows learners to explore different cybersecurity topics and perspectives through interactive simulations.

Intermediate Level

- **Module 3: Social Engineering** – Provides a structured, practical introduction to the techniques and risks associated with social engineering, one of the most common and effective methods used in cyberattacks today.
- **Module 4: Network Security Essentials and Penetration Testing for SMEs** – Provides trainees with an intensive, practical introduction to network security and basic penetration testing techniques tailored for SMEs.
- **Module 5: Software Security & Code Auditing** – Offers a structured, practical introduction to software security and focuses on secure coding principles, DevSecOps practices, vulnerability identification, and the use of appropriate tools for hands-on code analysis.

The NERO organisation page on the Digital Skills and Jobs Platform is available here:

<https://digital-skills-jobs.europa.eu/en/community/networking/organisations/nero-advanced-cybersecurity-awareness-ecosystem-smes>

The NERO project (AdvaNced cybErsecurity awaReness ecOsystem for SMEs) addresses the growing cybersecurity challenges faced by small and medium enterprises (SMEs), which often lack the resources and expertise to effectively manage cyber risks. As cyber threats continue to increase in scale and sophistication, there is a critical need for accessible, practical, and scalable solutions tailored to SMEs.

Through its ecosystem—including the [NERO Marketplace](#)—targeted training, tools, and awareness initiatives, NERO delivers practical, scalable solutions that strengthen cybersecurity skills and promote a security-first culture. Aligned with the European Cybersecurity Skills Framework (ECSF), the project contributes to enhancing digital resilience and supporting the cybersecurity capacity of SMEs across Europe.

“Making these training modules accessible through the Digital Skills & Jobs Platform helps SMEs across Europe build practical cybersecurity skills and strengthen their resilience against evolving cyber threats,” Dr Kitty Kioskli, NERO Project Coordinator.

[Discover the NERO Trainings on the Digital Skills and Jobs Platforms](#)

About NERO

The NERO Consortium is an EC-funded initiative (Grant Agreement No. 101127411) supported by the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre (ECCC), aimed at improving cybersecurity capacities, awareness and resilience across sectors, including SMEs.

For more information about the NERO Training:

- Visit <https://nerocybersecurity.eu>
- Follow us on X [@NEROCybersec](#) and LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/nero-cybersecurity>

=== END ===